

Chromatography of aromatic amines on thin layers of zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G with hybrid CTAB-alcohol-water mobile phase

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Thin layer chromatography (TLC) of twenty aromatic amines on zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G with CTAB or Brij 35-alcohol-water mobile phases has been studied. The effect of surfactant (CTAB) concentration below and above its critical micellar concentration on the rate of migration of amines (R_F value) was examined. On the basis of differential rate of migration (R_F value) some analytically important separations of aromatic amines were achieved. The method has also been applied for separation and semiquantitative determination of aromatic amines.

The use of synthetic inorganic ion exchangers as stationary phase is increasing in thin layer chromatography due to selective, sharp and rapid separations of organic compounds¹ and metal ions². Zinc ferrocyanide has been reported as an inorganic ion exchanger selective for Cs^+ ³. The practical utility of metal salt impregnated thin layers is restricted due to the formation of occasional tailing of spots, lesser stability in acidic solvent system, and tendency to absorb moisture. On the other hand, TLC methods involving the use of mixed organic solvent systems containing benzene, carbon tetrachloride, dioxane and hexane⁴ involve the risk of toxic effect. Therefore, it is important to develop less expensive, reliable and relatively non-toxic mobile phases for TLC. The present paper describes a systematic approach for the improved separations of aromatic amines on thin layers of zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G using cationic cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) surfactant.

Results and discussion

The mobilities (i.e. R_F values) of aromatic amines were determined on the thin layers of zinc ferrocyanide (ZFC)-silica gel G (SG) in the presence and absence of surfactant (CTAB). The mobile phases used were M_1 - M_3 and M_6 . Compositions of solvent systems used as mobile phase are as follows : M_1 , 0.25% (v/v) CH_3COOH in H_2O ; M_2 , 0.2% (w/v) CTAB in aq. CH_3COOH (0.25% v/v); M_3 , 0.5% (v/v) CH_3OH in aq. CH_3COOH (0.25% v/v); M_4 , 0.1 ml (CTAB + CH_3OH) + 99.25 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_5 , 0.5 ml [CTAB + CH_3OH] + 99.25 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_6 , 1.2 ml [CTAB + CH_3OH] + 98.55 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_7 , 2.4 ml [CTAB + CH_3OH] + 97.35 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_8 , 3.6 ml [CTAB + CH_3OH] + 96.15 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_9 , 1.2 ml [CTAB + C_2H_5OH] + 98.55 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_{10} , 1.2 ml [CTAB + C_3H_7OH] + 98.55 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml

CH_3COOH ; M_{11} , 1.2 ml [CTAB + C_4H_9OH] + 98.55 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH ; M_{12} , 1.2 ml [Brij-35 + CH_3OH] + 98.55 ml H_2O + 0.25 ml CH_3COOH . The observed R_F values are summarized in Table 1(a).

Table 1(a). Mobility (i.e. R_F) of amines in the presence and absence of surfactant in the mobile phase

Amines	R_F Values			
	M_1	M_2	M_3	M_6
<i>o</i> -TLD	0.68	0.75	0.82	0.79
<i>m</i> -TLD	0.65	0.73	0.80	0.76
<i>p</i> -TLD	0.20	0.22	0.27	0.26
AL	0.69	0.78	0.87	0.84
<i>o</i> -NAL	0.52	0.61	0.69	0.66
<i>m</i> -NAL	0.24	0.30	0.40	0.34
<i>p</i> -NAL	0.50	0.56	0.65	0.62
<i>o</i> -BAL	0.18	0.20	0.28	0.24
<i>m</i> -BAL	0.34	0.37	0.40	0.41
<i>p</i> -BAL	0.30	0.35	0.42	0.40
<i>o</i> -ANS	0.70	0.78	0.80	0.81
<i>m</i> -ANS	0.64	0.72	0.80	0.79
<i>o</i> -ABA	0.72	0.84	0.90	0.91
<i>m</i> -ABA	0.60	0.70	0.81	0.79
<i>p</i> -ABA	0.53	0.72	0.83	0.80
<i>o</i> -AP	0.60	0.74	0.90	0.88
<i>m</i> -AP	0.71	0.73	0.75	0.77
<i>p</i> -AP	0.65	0.78	0.83	0.77
<i>o</i> -CAL	0.32	0.42	0.45	0.43
<i>m</i> -CAL	0.20	0.34	0.41	0.36
DPA	0.38	0.49	0.52	0.53
ID	0.63	0.70	0.76	0.72

The chromatographic studies of aromatic amines in different mobile phases revealed that the mobility (i.e. R_F) of amines was higher in M_2 (CTAB in 0.25% CH_3COOH) mobile phase in comparison to M_1 (0.25% CH_3COOH) mobile phase. The higher mobility of most of the amines in the mobile phase M_3 compared with their mobility in M_1 seems due to the increased solubility of amines in methanol compared to 0.25% CH_3COOH . The R_F values of amines differ marginally when M_3 (MeOH + H_2O + CH_3COOH) is replaced by M_2 (CTAB + H_2O + CH_3COOH) or M_6 (CTAB + MeOH + H_2O + CH_3COOH) and the development time increased from 15 to 20 min for 10 cm ascent. The compactness of the spots also increased with the increased concentration of CTAB. This is probably due to the micelle formation, where the amines are trapped. CTAB being a cationic surfactant is considered to be adsorbed by zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G through ion exchange. Hence, the mobility of amines (R_F) decreased with the increased concentration of CTAB.

The R_F values summarized in Table 1(b) demonstrate how the mobility of amines is controlled by the composi-

tion of the four components (i.e. H_2O -MeOH-CTAB- CH_3COOH) in the mobile phase. The concentration of each component except CH_3COOH was varied in the mobile phases (M_4 - M_8), keeping total volume constant (100 ml). Depending upon the position of the mobile phase, the development time for 10 cm ascent was 17–33 min.

The reported critical micellar concentration (CMC) value of CTAB in water is $9.8 \times 10^{-4} M^5$. On the basis of R_F values studied in M_4 - M_8 systems having varying concentrations of CTAB i.e. from 0.55 to 19.75 mM (Table 1(a) and (b)), it is concluded that mixed mobile phases composed of cationic surfactant (CTAB), alcohol, water and acetic acid are suitable for separation of aromatic amines if the CTAB concentration in the mobile phase is kept below or just above to its CMC value.

Taking into consideration better separation possibilities, spot compactness and detection clarity of amines on zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G layer, mobile phase containing 0.24% CTAB (M_6) was selected for detailed studies.

Table 1(b). Mobility of amines on zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G layer with CTAB-methanol- H_2O - CH_3COOH mobile phase

Amines	R_F Values				
	M_4	M_5	M_6	M_7	M_8
<i>o</i> -TLD	0.87	0.85	0.79	0.77	0.69
<i>m</i> -TLD	0.83	0.82	0.76	0.76	0.66
<i>p</i> -TLD	0.42	0.42	0.38	0.30	0.19
AL	0.91	0.90	0.84	0.81	0.74
<i>o</i> -NAL	0.68	0.68	0.66	0.63	0.60
<i>m</i> -NAL	0.38	0.37	0.34	0.32	0.30
<i>p</i> -NAL	0.67	0.66	0.62	0.59	0.57
<i>o</i> -BAL	0.28	0.28	0.24	0.20	0.14
<i>m</i> -BAL	0.50	0.46	0.41	0.39	0.35
<i>p</i> -BAL	0.52	0.47	0.40	0.34	0.31
<i>o</i> -ANS	0.90	0.90	0.81	0.73	0.54
<i>m</i> -ANS	0.85	0.82	0.79	0.71	0.66
<i>o</i> -ABA	0.95	0.94	0.91	0.86	0.74
<i>m</i> -ABA	0.84	0.82	0.79	0.70	0.64
<i>p</i> -ABA	0.93	0.90	0.80	0.74	0.61
<i>o</i> -AP	0.94	0.92	0.88	0.85	0.79
<i>m</i> -AP	0.95	0.95	0.77	0.64	0.53
<i>p</i> -AP	0.84	0.84	0.77	0.73	0.65
<i>o</i> -CAL	0.55	0.51	0.43	0.41	0.39
<i>m</i> -CAL	0.50	0.48	0.36	0.34	0.30
DPA	0.60	0.59	0.53	0.49	0.41
ID	0.83	0.80	0.72	0.56	0.53

Table 1(c). Mobility of amines on zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G layer with CTAB- H_2O - CH_3COOH -alcohol (methanol, ethanol, butanol or propanol) and Brij-35- H_2O - CH_3COOH - CH_3O mobile phases

Amines	R_F Values				
	M_6	M_8	M_{10}	M_{11}	M_{12}
<i>o</i> -TLD	0.79	0.76	0.78	0.77	0.74
<i>m</i> -TLD	0.76	0.71	0.74	0.73	0.71
<i>p</i> -TLD	0.38	0.28	0.34	0.29	0.28
AL	0.84	0.79	0.82	0.80	0.76
<i>o</i> -NAL	0.66	0.56	0.61	0.60	0.61
<i>m</i> -NAL	0.34	0.32	0.33	0.32	0.30
<i>p</i> -NAL	0.62	0.54	0.60	0.56	0.57
<i>o</i> -BAL	0.24	0.12	0.22	0.15	0.13
<i>m</i> -BAL	0.41	0.31	0.38	0.34	0.35
<i>p</i> -BAL	0.40	0.28	0.34	0.36	0.30
<i>o</i> -ANS	0.81	0.62	0.75	0.69	0.70
<i>m</i> -ANS	0.79	0.71	0.77	0.73	0.68
<i>o</i> -ABA	0.91	0.86	0.90	0.88	0.82
<i>m</i> -ABA	0.79	0.70	0.77	0.74	0.67
<i>p</i> -ABA	0.80	0.74	0.79	0.76	0.75
<i>o</i> -AP	0.88	0.70	0.80	0.72	0.80
<i>m</i> -AP	0.77	0.67	0.72	0.69	0.63
<i>p</i> -AP	0.77	0.72	0.75	0.73	0.72
<i>o</i> -CAL	0.43	0.31	0.45	0.36	0.38
<i>m</i> -CAL	0.36	0.21	0.30	0.27	0.30
DPA	0.53	0.45	0.50	0.47	0.43
ID	0.72	0.63	0.69	0.69	0.59

The order of mobility (R_F values) of amines in different alcohols is $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} > \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} > \text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH} > \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$. This behaviour may be due to solubility variation of amines as well as CTAB in different alcohols. *o*-Bromoaniline is more strongly retained by the stationary phase ($R_F = 0.12\text{--}0.24$) irrespective of the type of alcohol present in mobile phase and hence can be separated from other investigated amines. *o*-Aminobenzoic acid (0.91) and *o*-aminophenol (0.88) can be separated from most of the amines in M_6 mobile phase.

The separations, which on the basis of R_F values in Table 1(c), were likely to be effective were tried, those achieved experimentally are summarized in Table 2. The spots obtained were compact and separations were clear.

Table 2. Separations achieved on zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G thin layers

Mixture	Eluent	R_F values
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	M_6	0.78
<i>p</i> -Toluidine		0.38
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	M_6	0.75
<i>p</i> -Toluidine		0.36
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	M_6	0.66
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline		0.33
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	M_6	0.62
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline		0.34
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	M_6	0.24
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline		0.42
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	M_6	0.24
<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline		0.40
Diphenylamine	M_6	0.53
Indole		0.72
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	M_6	0.22
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline		0.60
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol		0.88
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	M_6	0.80
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid		0.92
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	M_9	0.21
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline		0.31
<i>p</i> -Aminophenol		0.72

In order to examine the effect of non-ionic surfactant on the mobility of amines, Brij-35 replaced CTAB in M_6 mobile phase. The R_F values generally decreased in the mobile phase M_{12} containing Brij-35 compared to their R_F values in CTAB (M_6). An attempt has also made for the semiquantitative determination of *m*-anisidine by spot area measurement method. Standard solutions (0.01 ml) of *m*-anisidine (0.5–2%) were spotted on zinc ferrocyanide-silica

gel G thin layer. After spraying the developed chromatograms, the spot area was measured. A relationship between the area and microgram quantities of *m*-anisidine follows the empirical equation :

$$A^3 = Km$$

where, A is the spot area, m is the spotted amount (μg) and K is the constant. The linearity was maintained upto 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{spot}$ of *m*-anisidine. However, at higher concentration a negative deviation from linear law was obtained.

Experimental

Apparatus : A TLC apparatus (Toshnival, Mumbai, India), $20 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ glass plates and $25 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$ glass jars were used. Silica gel G, *N*-cetyl-*N,N,N*-trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and Brij-35 (S.D. Fine Chemicals, India), aromatic amines, methanol, ethanol and propanol (CDH, Mumbai, India) were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Amines used in this experiment are : *o*-toluidine (*o*-TLD), *m*-toluidine (*m*-TLD), *p*-toluidine (*p*-TLD), aniline (AL), *o*-nitroaniline (*o*-NAL), *m*-nitroaniline (*m*-NAL), *p*-nitroaniline (*p*-NAL), *o*-bromoaniline (*o*-BAL), *m*-bromoaniline (*m*-BAL), *p*-bromoaniline (*p*-BAL), *o*-anisidine (*o*-ANS), *m*-anisidine (*m*-ANS), *o*-aminobenzoic acid (*o*-ABA), *m*-aminobenzoic acid (*m*-ABA), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (*p*-ABA), *o*-aminophenol (*o*-AP), *m*-aminophenol (*m*-AP), *p*-aminophenol (*p*-AP), *o*-chloroaniline (*o*-CAL), *m*-chloroaniline (*m*-CAL), diphenylamine (DPA) and indole (ID). Test solutions of all amines (1%, w/v) were prepared in methanol. Amines were detected with *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-amino benzaldehyde (5%) in ethanol-glacial acetic acid (5 : 1, v/v).

Zinc ferrocyanide (ZFC) was prepared by mixing 10 ml each of zinc chloride solution (1.5 *M*) and potassium ferrocyanide solution (0.5 *M*). The mixture was stirred for 30 min using a magnetic stirrer. Then, 10 g of silica gel G (SG) was added to it and stirring was further continued for 60 min to obtain a homogeneous slurry of zinc ferrocyanide-silica gel G. The resultant slurry was applied on the glass plates with the help of an applicator to give 0.25 mm thick layer. The plates were first dried at room temperature and then activated at $100 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in a hot air oven for 1 h. The activated plates were kept in a closed glass chamber at room temperature. About 10 μL of amine solution was spotted on the thin layer plates with the help of micropipette. The plates were developed in a chosen developing system by the ascending technique. The solvent ascent was 10 cm in all the cases. After development, the TLC plates were taken out from the glass jars and dried at room temperature. The detecting reagent was sprayed on the TLC plates. The amines

were detected as yellow brown spots. The R_L (R_F of leading front) and R_T (R_F of tailing front) values of each spot were determined and the R_F values were calculated.

$$R_F = \frac{R_L + R_T}{2}$$

The R_F values reported in Tables 1(a-c) were calculated for the compact spots where the difference between R_L and R_T values was less than 0.3 cm.

For semiquantitative determination by the spot area measurement method, 0.01 ml from a series of standard solutions of *m*-anisidine (0.5–2%) were spotted on the thin layer of SG-ZFC. The plates were developed with the mobile phases M_5 . After detection, the spots were copied onto tracing paper from the chromatoplates. The tracing paper was placed on a sheet of millimeter graph paper and spot area was measured by counting the squares of graph paper.

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